

Prob(e1)Prob(e2) = Prob(e3)Prob(e4) and Quantum Spin

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In a previous note (1), we argued that even in classical mechanics one may introduce probability for free particles which collide. If the collision is elastic, kinetic energy is conserved and momentum is always conserved. Such a probability is imaginary because it is linked to dynamic particles which are not in equilibrium. Rather it is linked to conservation of momentum and energy, but to more than that. It is based on the idea that any e_1, e_2 pair has the same probability as an e_3, e_4 pair if $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ and any p_{x1}, p_{x2} pair has the same probability as any p_{x3}, p_{x4} pair if $p_{x1} + p_{x2} = p_{x3} + p_{x4}$ (and the same result for the p_y and p_z). This is the same basic statistical feature present in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, but there one has real probabilities $C \exp(-e_i/T)$ because energy is being distributed. We thus stress that this $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ for $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ is a key idea associated with the free particle $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r)$ whose argument is Lorentz invariant with the function \exp then being a scalar, i.e. dynamical probability has the same value in different frames.

The topic of this note, however, is quantum spin and we suggest that this same statistical idea is linked to spin. In order to obtain spin in the first place, we note that the classical vector p vector means that p_x is now linked to $-i\hbar/dx$ and $\exp(i(p_x)x)$ and similar results for (p_y) and (p_z) . Now (p_i) is the weight of a unit vector in linear algebra. In other words, weights and unit vectors belong to the mathematical field of linear algebra. If in the dynamical probabilistic case, one decides that (p_j) is obtained from $-i\hbar d/dx_j$ and $\exp(i(p_j)x_j)$ (no sum on j), for consistency, this suggests introducing an operator to take the place of the unit vector e_j associated with the j direction. In the case of $-EE = ppcc + momocccc$, linearizing to show the spatial features leads to the Pauli matrices. Dirac and Pauli have both dealt with this idea. The point we wish to make here, is that like with $\exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i p_3 x) \exp(i p_4 x)$ if $p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4$, the group theory properties of the operators replacing the e_j basis vectors is the same as that for angular momentum $r \times p$ and in that case, one may see explicitly that $\exp(i m_1 \phi) \exp(i m_2 \phi) = \exp(i m_3 \phi) \exp(i m_4 \phi)$, i.e. the same statistical feature which exists for $\exp(ipx)$. Thus, spin is not simply linked to finding eigenvectors of the operators which replace the unit vectors e_j (and which are linked to some kind of strange angular motion features although not rotation in a 2π circle), but seems to also be linked to the idea of statistical loss of information, i.e. $p(e_1)p(e_2) = p(e_3)p(e_4)$ for $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$, but with the z component of spin being mathematically linked to the $\exp(i m \phi)$ angular case. That is not to say that $\exp(i m \phi)$ represents spin, but it is the analogue of the projection in the angular momentum case which has the same group properties as the spin operators. As a result, we argue that there is an underlying statistical feature to spin similar to the $\exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i p_3 x) \exp(i p_4 x)$ situation.

Free Particle Dynamical Probability, Conservation and Key Statistical Feature

In (1), we argued that even free particles, which are not in equilibrium, collide in such a way that there may be conservation of energy (elastic collision) and momentum. If one introduces a probability based on the idea that any e_i, e_j pair and (p_{x1}, p_{x2}) pair have the same probability as

any other pair with the same sum, then this is a basic statistical feature found in the Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) ideal gas case for which:

$$p(e_1)p(e_2)=p(e_3)p(e_4) \text{ if } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \quad ((1))$$

In other words, this dynamical probability could be introduced in Newtonian mechanics to deal with collisions.

In the MB case, energy is distributed over N particles, so p(e) is real, but there is no reason for a real weight for free particles. The idea that:

$$\text{Number power conserved quantity} \quad ((2))$$

should hold so that product probabilities yield the probability ((1)) may also be applied to a complex $\exp(i \text{ conserved quantity})$ expression. The problem, as noted in (1), is that p is a vector and there is no reason for the direction of the x-axis to define the value of the probability. This suggests that p be multiplied to a linear measure linked with the x-axis, i.e. δx . Then one has:

$$\exp(i (px) \delta x) \quad ((3))$$

This frees the expression from the co-ordinate system. A more general freeing is from frames through the use of special relativity, i.e as noted in (1), one may use:

$$\exp(-iEt) \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}) \quad ((4))$$

The Case for Spin Operators

We note that \exp is then a scalar function and $-Et+px$, a Lorentz invariant. If one wishes to obtain the value of E or p, one may use the operators:

$$i \frac{d}{dt} \text{ partial} \text{ and } -i \text{ grad} \quad ((5))$$

Now, derivatives and derivatives combined with unit basis vectors, as in the grad case, exist in classical physics. We have introduced a probability ((4)) here to describe the system. Equations from classical physics, like $-EE = \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{p} \text{ cc} + \text{momo cccc}$, involve the vector p in a dot product etc. If one wishes to change E and p into operators, then these operators ((5)), acting on ((4)) essentially give the weights (px), (py) and (pz) which would then be multiplied by unit basis vectors \mathbf{e}_j ($\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z$). We argue, however, that it is inconsistent to use an operator-function scheme to obtain the weights of a vector and then introduce the \mathbf{e}_j basic vectors. Rather, the basis vectors should also be linked with an operator which acts on a function (or vector). This, we argue, is the motivation for spin, and based on this argument alone one may find the operators, as Dirac did by linearizing:

$$-E + p \cdot p = -m^2 c^2 \quad ((6))$$

These operators are linked with the Pauli matrices, which have certain mathematical properties which are given in the literature (2). The issue we wish to consider is the feature of

$$\exp(i p_1 x) \exp(i p_2 x) = \exp(i p_3 x) \exp(i p_4 x) \text{ if } p_1 + p_2 = p_3 + p_4 \quad ((7))$$

etc. We argued that this was the underlying idea for introducing a dynamic probability (i.e quantum mechanics for free particles) in the first place. This approach led to p_x being replaced by $-i\hbar/dx$ and $\exp(ipx)$. If one replaces basis vectors with a matrix and eigenvectors, then is there any statistical feature like the described directly above present? That is the key question we wish to consider.

Underlying Statistical Feature to Spin?

From (2), one may see that the Pauli matrices satisfy:

$$[s_j, s_k] = 2i \epsilon_{jkl} s_l \text{ where } \epsilon_{jkl} \text{ is the Levi-Civita symbol and } [] \text{ the commutator} \quad ((8))$$

We argue that ((7)) is a math form linked to group theory. If one considers independently the angular momentum operator (not linked a priori with spin), but introduced through:

$$R \times p \text{ with } p \rightarrow (-i\hbar/dx, -i\hbar/dy, -i\hbar/dz) \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{then from (3): } [L_l, L_m] = i\hbar \epsilon_{lmn} L_n \quad ((10))$$

In other words, spin and angular momentum share the same group theoretical features. This, however, may seem to have nothing to do with the property ((7)). We note, however, that for the case of angular momentum, the eigenfunction of L_z is $\exp(i m \phi)$ which has the same property as ((7)). Thus, the feature ((7)), which we argue leads to the creation of dynamical probabilities, i.e free particle quantum mechanics, does seem to be linked to the case of spin, even though one cannot use $\exp(i m \phi)$ to describe spin. It applies to L_z (angular momentum), but angular momentum has the same math structure as spin which is why one may write:

$$J = L + S \text{ where } L \text{ is the angular momentum operator and } S, \text{ the spin} \quad ((11)).$$

Thus, we argue that the statistical feature ((7)) is inherent in spin and is in fact a key underlying idea.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may assign complex probabilities to free particles (not real because there is no equilibrium). These complex probabilities do not simply enforce conservation of energy and momentum (elastic scattering), but ensure that any e_i, e_j with the

same sum have the same product probability and any $(p_x)_i, (p_x)_j$ pair with the same sum have the same product probability (and the identical feature for p_y, p_z). This leads to a scalar function with a Lorentz invariant argument: $\exp(-iEt + ip \cdot r)$.

We argue that to obtain p and E which appear in numerous equations, one must now use $\partial/\partial t$ partial for E and $-i \text{grad}$ for p ($\hbar=1$) together with $\exp(-iEt + ipx)$. The weights of p_j are linked with e_j basis vectors (and (p, E) is 4-vector). If these weights are linked with operators and associated functions, we suggest that the basis vectors should also. This leads to “spin” operators which are linked to Pauli matrices as shown by Dirac (Pauli etc). The issue which we wish to point out is that the spin (the Pauli matrices) have the same group theoretic structure as angular momentum which is introduced independently of spin through $r \times p$. A key feature is that the eigenfunctions of L_z are $\exp(i m \phi)$ which have the same statistical property as $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$. Thus, even though $\exp(i m \phi)$ is not used for spin, the mathematical features are linked and the statistical feature of $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ seems to carry over to spin as well. In other words, spin, like $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-iEt)$ is strongly linked to the Maxwell-Boltzmann notion of product probabilities (in their case $p(e_i)p(e_j) = p(e_k)p(e_l)$ for $e_i + e_j = e_k + e_l$), i.e. the same underlying statistical feature is present, we argue.

References

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3. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Angular_momentum_operator